

IJCS PUBLICATION (IJCSPUB.ORG)

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CURRENT SCIENCE (IJCSPUB)

An International Open Access, Peer-reviewed, Refereed Journal

Seasonal density variation, flock size and budgeting behaviour of Indian peafowl (*Pavo cristatus*) in Ambala, Haryana, India.

*Divya Jain

Dept of Botany, S.D. College, Ambala Cantt.

Sarita Rana

Dept of Zoology, IIHS, Kurukshetra University, Kurukshetra.

Abstract

There is little scientific evidence to support the overall status, habitat preference, and behaviour of the Indian peafowl, despite its widespread distribution across the country. The present study aimed to assess the seasonal change in density, flock size and time -activity budget of Indian peafowl (*Pavo cristatus*) in the Ambala district of Haryana from March 2021 to June 2022. The density of Indian peafowl was highest in the summer and lowest in the autumn. The woodlands had the largest flock sizes, whereas wasteland regions had the lowest flock sizes. It was observed that Indian peafowl spent the most time feeding and displaying, and the least time preening. The outcomes of the study could be used to develop more effective management and conservation strategies for Indian peafowl.

Key words: peafowl, seasonal density variation, flock size, budgeting behaviour

Introduction

The Indian peafowl *Pavo cristatus*, is a species of bird in the genus *Pavo* of the Phasianidae family. They are most notable for the male's extravagant tail, which it displays as part of courtship (Harikrishnan, S. *et. al.* 2010). The male is called a peacock, the female a peahen. Peafowl are unusual amongst the Galliformes in their capacity for sustained flight. The large males are among the most beautiful gallinaceans (Naseer, 2018), due to their shimmering blue plumage, their feather crowns and their about 150 long tail feathers with lots of eye marks, which help in performing their courtship display (Chopra and Kumar, 2014). Behavioural activities of Indian peafowl influence the mating of peafowl in breeding season (Harikrishnan, S *et.al.* 2010). It is, therefore, important to

understand behavioural activities to predict its influence on population density and flock size in Indian peafowl (Chopra and Kumar, 2014).

Peafowl was declared the national bird of India in 1963 because of its rich religious and legendary involvements in Indian traditions. The bird is protected under Section 51, 1-A of the Wildlife Protection Act, 1972 and killing it is strictly prohibited. Current threats to the Indian peafowl are considerable, as it now occupies a highly fragmented range throughout the country. Additionally, the species is under threat due to industrial development, the demand for feathers and wild meat, conflict with farmers, and increased use of chemical fertilizers and pesticides (Deepan *et. al.*, 2021). Although these threats are believed to cause declining status in several peafowl stronghold areas, the extent and pattern of the effects in different parts of the country are inconsistent. In some parts of India, the population of Indian peafowl has gone up, and the birds are reported to be a nuisance to the farmers (Jose and Nameer, 2020). There aren't enough valid scientific studies on the population size, preferred habitats, and behaviour of Indian peafowl considering changing land use trends and climate change. The main objectives of this study are to investigate the habitat-use patterns of Indian blue peafowl, documentation of the flock size, and budgeting behaviour of Indian blue peafowl in district Ambala. The outcome of this study will give baseline data for devising management and conservation strategies for the Indian peafowl.

Study area and Methodology

Study was conducted in district Ambala 30.2862°N, 76.9643°E of Haryana during the period of March 2021 to June 2022. Ambala is an industrial town that is divided between Ambala City and Ambala Cantonment. Most of the nearby area is made up of agricultural fields and semi-barren wastelands. The major crops are rice, wheat, gram, mustard, sugarcane, and peanuts. The woodland patches, which were once broadly distributed, now only exist in a few places because of anthropogenic pressure. Important trees species found here are Kikar (*Acacia nilotica*), shisham (*Dalbergia sissoo*), teak (*Tectona grandis*), neem (*Azadirachta indica*), jamun (*Syzgium cumini*), pipal (*Ficus religiosa*), karanj (*Pongamia pinnata*), bargad (*Ficus bengalensis*) and bakayan (*Melia azedarach*). Safeda (*Eucalyptus hybrid*) and poplar (*Populus deltoides*) are grown on highways and private lands.

To map the current populations of Indian Peafowl in Ambala extensive reconnaissance surveys were conducted at Rani ka Talab, Hathikhana and Babyal. During these surveys, apart from recording the presence/absence of Indian Peafowl, data on land use practices was also collected. Information on Indian peafowl was also collected by interviewing local people. Based on the information provided by the local people, extensive surveys were conducted covering all the ranges of the study area.

Data was evaluated in different habitat types using line transect methods. From line transect data, density estimation was done using the software DISTANCE 4.1 for Windows (Buckland *et. al.*, 2001). Landscape assessment was done visually to stratify the area in each site into a few habitat types. Data on microhabitat variables were collected in a 0.05 ha (radius = 12.62 m) circular plots (Bibby *et al.* 1992) centered on the locations of sighted

Indian Peafowl on line transects. Tree density was collected by the dimension of number of trees in a circular plot with the trees of plot. Canopy cover (%) was estimated using a gridded mirror of 30 x 30 cm dimensions. One-way analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to analyze differences in densities of Indian Peafowl in breeding and non-breeding seasons. The chi-square test was used to test preference and avoidance of a given habitat by species in various blocks.

Results and discussion

For planning effective management for bird populations, population monitoring is a useful technique for assessing population trends. Usually, the index counts are designed to be easy to perform while still providing reasonably accurate and exact information on relative population levels (Bibby *et al.*, 1993, Jain and Rana, 2013). The estimation of bird population density from a line transect is now a well-established technique for determining bird population densities of different species (Burnham *et al.*, 1981). In our investigation, we found that there is great deal of variation observed in density of Indian peafowl in different seasons of the year. The density was found to be at its maximum in the summer and at its lowest in the autumn (Fig.1). Female population densities were found to be comparable throughout the winter and spring, but they differed significantly in the summer and autumn. Due to Indian peafowl's polygyny habit, the density of males was found to be substantially lower than that of females. The density of female Indian peafowl peaked in the summer at 15.8 birds per square kilometer, whereas it fell to 5.9 birds per square kilometer in autumn (Fig.1) The variation in group size during the season was shown to be statistically significant.

In our investigation, the peafowl's habitat use was significantly non-random, with woodland patches being the most utilized habitat, followed by croplands. Similar non-random habitat preferences in Indian peafowl have also been observed by Nay Myo Shwe *et al.* (2020). The woodland had the largest flock size, with an average of 6.5 birds, whereas wasteland areas had the smallest flocks, with an average of 2.4 birds (Table 2). Cropland also displayed a high group size of 5.3 birds, and it was determined that there was statistically significant variation in group size between the different habitats. Indian peafowl encounter rates with females, males, and chicks were highest in woodlands. On the other hand, cropland showed notable encounter rates for chicks, and both male and female Indian peafowl. In contrast habitats like wasteland and scrubland did not exhibit significant encounter rates (Table 2). Significant encounter rates between chicks, male and female Indian peafowl in croplands were also found by Dookia *et al.* (2015). Fukuhara *et al.* (2022) reported the fields dominated by members of Poaceae to be preferred nesting habitat of Indian peafowl. Our findings corroborate the observations by McGowan *et al.* (1995), Anwar *et al.* (2015), Ranjith and Jose (2016), Samson and Balasundaram (2018), Rajashekara and Venkatesha (2019), and Kaur and Kler (2020) showing that the species favors arid semi-desert grasslands, scrub, and deciduous forests.

Time budgeting behaviour of Indian peafowl was recorded in different behavioural activities such as resting, displaying, feeding, movement and preening during three different time periods of the day. Indian peafowl spent maximum time in feeding (58.07 ± 1.23) and displaying (51 ± 0.52) in morning hours whereas minimum time was spent in preening activities (4.62 ± 0.57) throughout the day (Table 2). Similar observations were reported by Kaur and Kler (2017) and Rajeshkumar and Balasubramanian (2012). Miazzi *et al.* (2020) have reported less time spent on feeding but more on preening and display by Indian peafowl in captivity. The observations may differ because captive birds are less constrained in their ability to find food. Display activity (32 ± 1.56) and feeding activity (24.60 ± 2.64) was found to reduce during afternoon hours (Table 2). According to Kaur and Kler, (2017) and Chaudhary *et al.* (2021), the Indian peafowl similarly preferred resting and occasionally grazing in the underbrush during the day but migrating into fields to forage more actively in the morning and evening. All roosting sites observed were in areas dominated by trees such as Kikar (*Acacia nilotica*), karanj (*Pongamia pinnata*), neem (*Azadirachta indica*), pipal (*Ficus religiosa*), bargad (*Ficus bengalensis*) and bakayan (*Melia azedarach*). The birds preferred the trees that were tall, had broad trunk, and greater height of the first branch for roosting. Kaur and Kler (2020) reported similar preference of roosting sites by Indian peafowl in Chandigarh, the neighboring city of Ambala.

Fig. 1. Seasonal variation in Density of Indian peafowl in study sites.

Table 1. Flock size of peafowl in various habitats.

Habitat	N	Encounter rates/hectare			Flock size	Dominant vegetation
		Female	Male	chicks		
Waste land	36	2.3	2.1	Nil	2.4	Grass
Cropland	48	8.1	3.6	5	5.3	Wheat
Scrubland	45	6.8	2.3	Nil	3.9	Sarkanda
Woodland patch	53	11.2	3.8	7	6.5	Kikar

Table 2. Budgeting behaviour of Indian peafowl to perform various activities.

Time Period	Number of Observations (N)	Resting	Displaying	Feeding	Movement	Preening
Morning	52	26.72 ±2.76	51±0.52	58.07 ± 1.23	25.31± 0.89	2.91 ± 0.50
Afternoon	48	24.60 ±2.64	32±1.56	32.83 ± 2.37	23.19 ± 0.79	7.96 ± 1.06
Evening	56	29.48 ±3.51	33±0.17	52.56 ± 1.27	24.18 ± 1.03	2.99 ± 0.45
Total	156	23.27± 1.87	69± 1.00	47.82± 2.78	24.23 ± 0.53	4.62± 0.57
P-Value		0.27	0.00	0.00	0.27	0.00

Fig. 2 Behavioural activities in Indian peafowl: A-Feeding, B- Alert, C-Display, D- Roosting

Conclusion

According to the observations, scrub forests are the preferred habitat for peafowl in Haryana. The bird prefers to roost on tall and broad trees. The woodland patches in the Ambala zone are only found in isolated places because of anthropogenic pressures like the need for more arable land and urbanization. Therefore, habitat loss and fragmentation are the main factors contributing to the peafowl population decline in Haryana. The size of the flock, the efficacy of the signaling, and the cost of display are all influenced by how much time Indian peafowl spends feeding, resting, moving, and staying alert. There is a need to conduct in-depth research on the Indian peafowl's time-activity budget as the behaviour depends on the bird's habitat selection.

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